

TEMPERATURE INFLUENCE ON CARBON NANOTUBES AS A TIP OF ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPY PROBES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the geometrical and structural behaviors of single-walled carbon nanotube, which is designed as the tip of the Atomic Force Microscopy probe, are examined by molecular dynamics simulation. Armchair and Zig-Zag type of nanotubes were simulated in the various temperature (300K, 500K, 700K, and 900K) conditions. The systems were studied using a molecular dynamics model with the software, Hyperchem[®], employing an empirical MM+ force field. In our results, both types of CNTs experienced twisting and bending behaviors during simulations and the degree of both situations altered with increasing temperature. Also, it is found that armchair CNT is more susceptible to bending while zig-zag type is in twisting at high temperature condition. However, the results obtained from Hyperchem[®] only provide a general idea of what may happen instead of a promise in the simulations as similar behaviors are observed under different loading conditions with higher temperature in numerous studies.

KEYWORDS: Carbon nanotubes, geometrical behavior, temperature variation.

INTRODUCTION

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is believed to be a powerful technique to examine surface topography of materials in nanoscale. However, the resolution of AFM images is strongly depended on AFM's tip geometry such as its diameter and aspect ratio [1]. Conventional AFM tips made of silicon or silicon nitride can not produce high resolution images as they are easily worn out and changed in diameter, particularly when pressing on the surface of testing specimens [2].

Carbon nanotube (CNT) has been recently suggested as an ultimate high resolution probe for AFM due to their attractive physical and mechanical properties such as small diameter, high aspect ratio, large tensile modulus and mechanical robustness. Numerous studies already succeed in attaching nanotube bundles and an individual nanotube to AFM tip [3, 4]. Such probes can provide significant improvement of lateral resolution compared with conventional probe and have been applied for imaging and nano-lithography [5-7]. Moreover, wearing of sample surfaces can be minimized by employing a CNT tip and no detectable degradation of such probes has been observed after the long scanning process [2, 8].

The CNT probe tip may also provide advantages over the conventional probes when obtaining values for the roughness coefficient and lateral correlation length [9]. Biological molecules, such as DNA, can be visualized with high resolution using CNT tips [10]. And the damage caused by the AFM tips to the biological samples can be avoided because of the maximum force applied to a sample surface by the CNT tip is limited [11].

Although CNT has been expected to be promising probes for AFM, certain difficulties must be overcome before it can be widely accepted for applications. Alignment of the CNT on the probe is a crucial factor which may cause the probe to be deflected due to the surface-nanotube interaction during imaging. Also, the length of the CNT is shown to have strong influence on the interaction between the tip and a testing sample [12]. Apart from this, the temperature dependent behavior of CNTs may influence the scanning quality and accuracy at different temperatures. Radial shrinkage and coalescence of CNTs within a bundle are found to occur at high temperature [13, 14].

In this paper, we focused on the geometrical properties of CNTs at different temperatures. As during imaging with AFM, the detection of the surface depends on the bending and deflection of the CNT and the length of CNT tip permits the tracing of rough surface with steep and deep features, thus any change in length and structure integrity of CNT during temperature variation will seriously affect the accuracy of the measurement. Therefore, a better understanding of such properties is necessarily important before any applications in reality.

SIMULATION METHOD

In this work, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were carried out to predict the geometrical behavior by using the software Hyperchem[®]. This software employed a classical molecular dynamics method where numerous force fields and potential functions are provided. However, the 2nd Brenner potential function which is suggested to provide good accuracy in the simulation of various carbon structures [15] isn't available in Hyperchem[®]. Thus, the modified MM+ force field [16] that found to be closest to the 2nd Brenner is applied to simulate the interaction between atoms. Moreover, the leap frog algorithm is used in Hyperchem[®] to integrate the equations of motion in the MD simulations. Armchair (10,10) (as shown in Fig.1) and zig-zag (17,0) single-walled CNTs were applied in our models. Both ends of the CNTs with an aspect ratio of 1:12 were constrained in order to keep atoms in place for simulating their actual AFM probe imaging condition. The CNTs' models were stabilized using Polak-Ribiere conjugate gradient energy minimization method with RMS gradient 0.1 kcal/Åmol in 0K and temperatures of 300K, 500K, 700K and 900K were employed to simulate the testing conditions during MD simulations with the time step of 0.01fs for an overall time 30ps.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of the simulations are summarized and shown in Figs. 2 to 4. As mentioned before, the length of CNT plays a critical part in the imaging with AFM, thus the edge atoms at both ends of the CNT are restrained to model the actual situation. Under such conditions, twisting and bending of CNTs are observed in the simulations and the degree of both behaviors increase with the temperature. The geometrical changes in CNTs are shown in Fig. 2 while the original shape of CNT is present in Fig. 1 as a reference. A better picture of the variation in twisting and bending behaviors are indicated by the end views of CNTs in Fig. 3 and 4. By comparing the results of armchair and zig-zag CNTs, the temperature change is found to have a stronger influence on the zig-zag type. During the raise of temperatures, the original cylindrical shape of both types of CNT changed to a bent and twisted form. However, the bending effect is overtaking the twisting in armchair type and the degree of bending increased with temperature. For the zig-zag type, the phenomenon of twisting and bending are also observed; Nevertheless, the variation of such behaviors was different compared with that of

the armchair type. It was found that the effect on twisting is dominated in zig-zag CNTs, while bending is dominated in armchair type at high temperature condition. It is suggested that during the simulation, the atoms in CNT gained enough energy to escape from its original position and thus causing the distortion of the CNT tubes. However, due to the structural difference between zig-zag and armchair CNTs, unlike degree of distortion of CNTs were created. Therefore, in order to effectively employ CNTs as a tip of AFM probes at various temperature conditions, the thermal behavior of the CNTs must be studied carefully since any change in their length and structural rigidity can affect the interaction between a CNT tip and substrates. This may result in poor imaging resolution and even damage the CNT tip and sample's surface.

Although our simulated results suggested that both type of CNTs would undergo twisting and bending with increasing temperature, however, numerous studies have shown that similar kinds of phenomenon would occur when the nanotubes are under different loading conditions or together with raising temperature of the systems. This is less likely to our study as the CNTs change shape due to variation of temperature only.

Nardelli et. al [17,18] carried out classical and quantum MD simulation to study the properties of CNTs under axial tension. During simulation, different tensile strains were applied to the CNTs and the systems were heated to more than 1000K. After the initial equilibration, topological defects were found in CNTs as double pentagon-heptagon defects (5-7-7-5). And such defects might split into 5-7 edge dislocations or turn to higher order rings (e.g. 8-9 dislocation edge) depending on the applied strain and heating conditions. The creation of such defects causing alteration of the curvature in the CNTs and is shown in Fig. 5. By comparing it with Fig.6, the closer view of our simulated nanotube, it is interesting to observe the similarity in curvature variation of the CNT. However, the change in curvature in our simulated nanotube isn't due to the formation of topological defects as no defects are found in the simulated CNTs, hence such changes must due to some other reasons apart from defects.

Yakobson et. al [19] and Srivastava et. al [20] employed MD simulation with the Tersoff-Brenner Potential to examine the axial compression in CNTs. The CNTs under compressive strains experienced sideways buckling once the critical force is reached. When the applied strain increased, redistribution of the strain resulting in the extended buckling and localized kink formation were observed. Those buckled CNTs are shown as in Fig. 7-8. When compare these results with our simulated CNTs in fig. 2-4, it is suggested that there is some conditions in common between the cases.

The way that our simulated CNTs bend is surprisingly alike those in the compression models. In the compression simulations, the CNTS buckled due to the application of axial compressive load at the end of CNT. In our work, since the ends of CNT were constrained, thus no inward or outward movement is allowed for the edge atoms. The ability of bending indicates the bond lengths between atoms were increase which may due to the energy gain of atoms during the MD simulation. Besides, the twisting (change in curvature) occurred as mentioned earlier may also because of the raising of energy inside the atoms. The energy enriched atoms tried to move to the position where it find itself in the most stable state, therefore, a bended and twisted CNT was obtained in our simulation.

It is only some assumptions for our results; however, the exact reasons of such behavior are still uncertain. Different force field/potential function, diverse parameters used in the calculation, and unlike assumptions employ in the simulations always are the causes of the dissimilar results. In order to find the accurate behavior of CNTs in different temperature

conditions, further works are necessary on searching for the appropriate potential function/force field, modeling parameters and assumptions for the simulations.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, it shows that the geometrical and structural properties of the CNTs are varied with temperature. CNTs with different chiralities are found to have dissimilar influences by the temperature variations. These results point out possible caution when examining the materials at different temperatures with the use of CNT AFM tips. However, due to different assumptions and simulation schemes used, similar behaviors are observed under different loading condition with higher various temperatures in a number of studies. In order to resolve these uncertainties, a detailed analysis must be carried out on such similar results as well as those alike commercial software packages that normally use to carry out the molecular simulations. Although the length of the CNTs plays an important role in the AFM imaging, the end cap of the CNT is not negligible. Further works are on-going in investigating the influence of the shape of an end cap of CNTs to the tip-surface interaction at different temperatures. If the above problems are solved, we will have a better insight into the application of the CNT tip in real-life.

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REFERENCES

1. D. Keller, "Reconstruction of STM and AFM images distorted by finite-size tips", *Surf. Sci.* Vol. 253, No.1-3, 1991, pp.353-364
2. C. V. Nguyen, K. J. Chao, R. M. D. Stevens, L. Delzeit, "Carbon nanotube tip probes: stability and lateral resolution in scanning probe microscopy and application to surface science in semiconductors", *Nanotechnology* Vol. 12, 2001, pp.363-367
3. R. M. D Stevens, N. A. Frederick, B. L. Smith, D. E. Morse, "Carbon nanotubes as probes for atomic force microscopy", *Nanotechnology* Vol. 11, 2000, pp.1-5
4. H. J. Dai, J. H. Hafner, A. G. Rinzler, D. T. Colbert, "Nanotubes as nanoprobe in scanning probe microscopy", *Nature* Vol. 384, Iss. 6605, 1996, pp.147-150
5. S. S. Wong, A. T. Woolley, T. W. Odom, J. L. Huang, "Single-walled carbon nanotube probes for high-resolution nanostructure imaging", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* Vol. 73, 1998, pp.3465-3467
6. A. Okazaki, S. Akita, H. Nishijima, Y. Nakayama, "Nanolithography of organic polysilane films using carbon nanotube tips", *Jpn. J. of Appl. Phys.* Vol. 39, 2000, pp.3744-3746

7. N. Choi, T. Uchihashi, H. Nishijima, T. Ishida, "Atomic force microscopy of single-walled carbon nanotubes using carbon nanotube tip", *Jpn. J. of Appl. Phys.* Vol. 39, 2000, pp.3707-3710
8. L. Q. Guo, J. Liang, S. Dong, Z. W. Xu, Q. L. Zhao, "Property of carbon nanotube tip for surface topography characterization", *Appl. Surf. Sci.* Vol. 228, 2004, pp.53-56
9. Q. M. Hudspeth, K. P. Nagle, Y. P. Zhao, T. Karabacak, "How does a multiwalled carbon nanotube atomic force microscopy probe affect the determination of surface roughness statistics?", *Surf. Sci.* Vol. 515, 2002, pp.453-461
10. K. Umemura, J. Komatsu, T. Uchihashi, N. Choi, "Atomic force microscopy of RecA-DNA complexes using a carbon nanotube tip", *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* Vol. 281, 2001, pp.390-395
11. H. Nishijima, S. Kamo, S. Akita, Y. Nakayama, "Carbon-nanotube tips for scanning probe microscopy: Preparation by a controlled process and observation of deoxyribonucleic acid", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* Vol. 74, 1999, pp.4061-4063
12. E. S. Snow, P. M. Campbell, J. P. Novak, "Single-wall carbon nanotube atomic force microscope probes", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* Vol. 80, No. 11, 2002, pp.2002-2004
13. Y. Yosida, "Radial shrinkage of single-walled carbon nanotube bundles at high temperatures", *The Rigaku Journal* Vol. 19, No. 1, 2002, pp.42-46
14. M. Terrones, H. Terrones, F. Banhart, J. C. Charlier, P. M. Ajayan, "Coalescence of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes", *Science* Vol. 288, Iss. 5469, 2000, pp.226-230
15. D. W. Brenner, "Empirical potential for hydrocarbons for use in simulating the chemical vapor deposition of diamond films", *Phys. Rev. B* Vol.42, 1990, pp.9458-9471
16. Hyperchem® Computational Chemistry, Hypercube, Inc., USA, 2002
17. Marco Buongiorno Nardelli, B. I. Yakobson, and J. Bernholc, "Mechanism of strain release in carbon nanotubes", *Phys. Rev. B* Vol. 57, 1998, pp.R4277-4280
18. Marco Buongiorno Nardelli, B. I. Yakobson, and J. Bernholc, "Brittle and Ductile Behavior in Carbon Nanotubes", *Phys. Rev. Lett.* Vol. 84, No. 21, 1998, pp.4656-4659
19. B. I. Yakobson, C. J. Brabec, and J. Bernholc, "Nanomechanics of Carbon Tubes: Instabilities beyond Linear Response", *Phys. Rev. Lett.* Vol. 76, No. 14, 1996, pp.2511-2514
20. Deepak Srivastava, Stephen T. Barnard, "Molecular dynamics simulation of large-scale carbon nanotubes on a shared-memory architecture", *Conference on High Performance Networking and Computing*, Proceedings of the 1997 ACM/IEEE conference on Supercomputing, pp. 1 - 10

Fig. 1: Simulated model of the armchair (10,10) CNT.

Fig. 2: Side view of the armchair (10,10) CNT at different temperatures

Fig. 3: End view of the armchair (10,10) CNT at different temperatures

Fig. 4: End view of zigzag (17,0) CNT at different temperatures

Fig. 5: Three snapshot of MD simulation of a CNT under different axial tensile strain and temperature [17]

Fig. 6: Enlarged side view of our simulated CNT

Fig. 7: MD simulated CNT with various compressive strain [19]

Fig. 8: MD simulated results of CNT with 8.5% compressive strain [20]